

IDENTIFICATION OF TWO TYPES OF ROTTEN MEAT USING AN ELECTRONIC NOSE FOR FOOD QUALITY CONTROL

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Abstract- Microorganisms are contained in all foods, some of them don't pose a risk for consumers, but many others became pathogenic, because of bad conservation or expired dates. Food will be degraded when the number of microorganisms became very large. The focus in this paper will be on the design of an electronic nose used in detecting rotten food. This nose is applied to detect bad odor diffused by rotten beef, and rotten chicken those meat have almost the same odor at rottenness which is not easily identified by human. Durations and gases emit of its rotten are determined by the pattern recognition methods PCA (Principal Components Analysis) for classification and DFA (Discriminate factorial analysis) for dating, and we will be identify between those rotten meat by DFA method.

Index terms: Electronic nose, rotten beef, rotten chicken, sensors, Principal Components Analysis, Discriminate Factorial Analysis, Pattern recognition system.

I. INTRODUCTION

Meat is a complex niche that has physical and chemical properties that allow the colonization and development of pathogenic microorganisms. Microbes exist in meat are influenced by many factors. After slaughtering, water, air, soil as well as operators and the equipment involved during the manufacturing process, are all factors that might potentially contribute to contaminate meat [1]. Point of spoilage is defined by the maximum acceptable bacterial level, unacceptable odor, or appearance for consumption. However, the common characteristics of spoilage contain foul odor and gas production. Nutrients available for bacteria on the surface and its high water content make meat one of the most perishable foods [2]. We focus in this paper on two types of meat which have almost the same smell at rottenness and the same microbes [3]: chicken and beef. The aim is to detect spoiled meat, identify its nature and provide information about its degradation level using an electronic nose.

An electronic nose system undertakes its task in two steps: collecting and processing signals issued from an array of gas sensors, to output a footprint of the odor, and then pattern recognition, when this foot print is analyzed [4-5].

We have different application domain of electronic nose particular, in medicine, agriculture, Environment, perfumes, drinks and the food quality control which is our work topic.

Recently a lot of researchers use an electronic nose for meat: Either to detect rotten meat, to identify deferent types of fresh meat or to compare between rotten and fresh meat of various types (rotten fish and fresh beef) [6-10].

In this paper an electronic nose is designed to identify rotten beef and rotten chicken. In second part, the methodology of the work is presented. In the third part, degradation of beef is studied during 11 days using PCA method for classification and DFA method for the identification of unknown sample. In the fourth part, the same study is done for chicken sample initially stored at 4 °C and chicken samples frosted. Finally, identification of the dating and type of unknown sample of two kinds of meat is realized.

II. THE PROPOSED ELECTRONIC NOSE FOR ROTTEN FOOD

Block diagram in Figure 1, illustrates the proposed electronic nose. This diagram is composed of odor handling system when samples are prepared, odor detection system based on a sensor array, that delivering odor footprint which is classified and identified by the pattern recognition system.

Figure 1. Electronic nose diagram

Diagram of the proposed electronic nose present,

- 1) The volatile organic compounds sample is prepared in odor handling system by the sampling techniques. These techniques are used to separate the constituents of liquid or gaseous mixture. In the literature the different techniques are used such as, static headspace, dynamic headspace, micro extraction [11-13]. In this paper the pre-concentration technique exactly dynamic headspace are used,
- 2) The volatiles compound coming of odor handling system is injected in odor detection system. In this block different types of sensors are used: for gas detection TGS, MQ [14], DHT11 for humidity and temperature sensing. These detectors are liaised with an Arduino Card. In the output, odor footprints are available,
- 3) Odor footprints are classified by principal components analysis (PCA) [15-17] and identified by discriminate factorial analysis (DFA) [18-20] for pattern recognition. An odor database is constructed from known samples to analyze the unknown samples by comparing.

III. METHODOLOGY

The proposed electronic nose system consists in two parts: hardware development where the electronic nose is designed and tested. In the second part we focus on software development where the pattern recognition system is tested by PCA and DFA methods.

a. Hardware Development

Metal oxide based gas sensors TGS and MQ types are used because of their fast response, high sensitivity and simple drive circuitry [21]. Humidity and temperature are measured by DHT11 digital sensor for system ambience control. All these sensors provide output signals which are processed by an ARDUINO card. Figure 2 shown, gas sensors circuits from TGS and MQ. Each sensor is fed at the input by a control voltage $V_C = 5 \text{ V}$ in order to measure the variation of conductance. These sensors are heated by integrated resistor under a $V_H = 5 \text{ V}$ voltage. In the presence of detectable gas, sensor conductivity increases. These changes in conductivity are converted to a voltage signal by the measuring circuits. Figure 3 shows electronic circuit diagram for the electronic nose. Thereafter, design of detection system as shown in the Figure 4.

Figure 2. From left to right: a) Basic detector circuit for TGS and MQ gas sensors. b) TGS and MQ gas sensors.

Figure 3. Electronic circuit diagram for the electronic nose

(a) sensor Array

(b) Detection system

Figure 4. Design of detector circuit

The different samples are treated sequentially by the odor detection system and the results are memorized by the recording system, as described by block diagram in Figure 5. The collected data are processed by software in the pattern recognition system.

Figure 5. Recording system diagram

Before starting the experiment, it's very important to supply the appropriate voltages for each sensor during fifteen minutes; that stabilizes the sensitive layer and allows a good repeatability of the measurements (sensor reset). Afterwards, a reference gas (nitrogen gas) is passed during ten minutes, in order to remove all the parasitic gases existing in the measuring cell and also to regenerate the sensors. To perform a good result, walls of measuring cell must be cleaned by a paper soaked with pharmaceutical hydrogen peroxide or an ethanol solution. In this experiment, each sample is individually placed in odor handling system. When equilibrium is reached, volatile compounds are collected and conveyed to the detection system by nitrogen gas. These volatile compounds must only be in contact with materials which present neither adsorption nor cause any degradation for these compounds. Temperature and humidity of measuring cell must be controlled during each measurement. For fixed temperature and humidity levels, voltages (V_1 ,

V2, V3, V4, V5) representing respectively the time response of each of the five gas sensors are available at the output of the detection system.

The same measurement cycle of 60 minutes is repeated for several meat samples at the same conditions, in order to develop a fairly large database. Subsequently to all these measurements an odor foot print is built. The results for the different samples are recorded in an SD card controlled by an ARDUINO module and processed later in the recognition system.

b. Software Development

In this part, the light is shed on the pattern-recognition system based on Principal Components Analysis for classification and Discriminate Factorial Analysis of identification. Before classification a database characterizing the different odor footprints is constructed. Generally, this database is in the form of a rectangular table (individual-variable table) where columns represent the p variables and lines the n individuals for which these variables are measured. The element X_{ij} of the database corresponds to the value of the variable j taken by the individual i (refer Figure 6).

Figure 6. Individual-variable table

PCA method consists to choosing the principal components axes. These axes are used to obtain a quite precise summary of the information contained in the database. The graphics are constructed to give a meaning for the new variables and provide an evaluation of the quality of this summary. This method is used to classify data in groups. DFA is a method of data analysis aiming to discriminate m groups of previously defined individuals, described by p quantitative variables. We will thus seek linear combinations of the p initial variables (discriminate axis) leading to the

best separation between groups. This allows, among other things, to describe the differences between these groups. A statistic software XLSTAT is used to implement the PCA and DFA methods.

IV. THE DEGRADATION OF BEEF

In this experiment, beef meat is cut in several identical pieces of 20g each and stored at 4 °C. Before every experiment, samples of beef are taken in the fridge and placed in odor handling system. When equilibrium is reached, the volatile compounds are collected and conveyed to the detection system by nitrogen gas (refer Figure 7). At the output of detection system we have the response of each gas sensor as a function of time, temperature and humidity.

Figure 8, shows the temporal response of the sensor array in the presence of beef samples during 11 days. The Organic Solvent Vapors are detected by TGS822 (refer Figure 8(a)), Hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) is detected by MQ136 (refer Figure 8(d)), Ammoniac is detected by MQ137 (refer Figure 8(b)), VOC (Mellow, Benzene, Aldehyde, acetone) are detected by MQ138 (refer Figure 8(c)) and Halocarbons are detected by MQ139 (refer Figure 8(e)). From Figure 8, it is concluded that the output voltage of each sensor increases between the third and fifth day.

Figure 7. Odor handling system diagram

(a) TGS822

(b) MQ137

(c) MQ138

(d) MQ136

(e) MQ139

Figure 8. The temporal response of the sensor array for beef

a. Classification by PCA method

Figure 9 represents the variables extracted from a typical temporal response of the used gas sensors:

- (1) V_0 (0 → 10 min): relates the mean value of the output voltage of each sensor in the first 10 minutes.
- (2) dV/dt (10 min → 20min): Is the dynamic slope of the response voltage curve in the time interval [10min → 20min].
- (3) V_s (55min → 60min): Is the average stabilized output voltage measured during the last 5 minutes.
- (4) A : Represents the area of the surface (calculated by the trapezoidal method).

Figure 9. Representation of the parameters extracted from the sensor temporal response

The four variables are used by PCA method giving a graphical representation of the separation into classes (groups). Figure 10, justifies the choice of the previous four variables, showing a correlation between the measures corresponding to a different beef storage periods.

Figure 10. Correlation circle between variables and factors for beef

From Figure 11, an overlap between the corresponding measurements is observed in day 1 (group 1 fresh beef), also for 3 and 5 days (group 2 starting to rot) and 7, 9 and 11 days (group 3 rotten beef).

Figure 11. Results of PCA method for beef degradation during 11 days

The Principal Component Analysis gives a graphical representation of the data in classes but doesn't give a decision rule to identify unknown samples, which is what DFA allows us to do.

b. Identification using DFA method

The DFA method can be used to identify unknown samples of beef (Duration of degradation) not belonging to the database but near to the measurements acquired in the learning phase. From Figure 12 we observe that the three groups are well separated, and the observations within the same class are quite grouped together. Indeed, the grouping of classes is actually quite distinct around their centers of gravity with 99.5% success of classification.

Figure 12. DFA method results for beef degradation during 11 days

Figure 13 compares the unknown samples with the data base. Degradation durations of the samples marked test1...test4 are unknown. Class1...class3 are results of known samples from the data base. Table 1 below shows the validation of our results for unknown samples. Distance between unknown samples and class of degradation are determined by the DFA method.

Figure 13. The result of DFA method for the unknown samples

Table 1: Unknown samples identification

Unknown Samples	Days (degradation duration)	Result of identification
Test1	* Day1	* Class 1 “Fresh”
Test2	* Day2	* Class 1 “Fresh”
Test3	* Day8	* Class 2 “Rotten”
Test4	* 5 days at freezer *Before 1 hour of thawing.	* Class 1 “Fresh”

V. THE DEGRADATION OF CHECKEN

The experiment of chicken is the same condition that beef. From Figure 14, it is concluded that the output voltage of each sensor increases between the third and fifth day.

(a) TGS822

(b) MQ137

(c) MQ138

(d) MQ136

(e) MQ139

Figure 14. The temporal response of array sensor for chicken

a. Classification by PCA method

The same principle as beef, the circles of correlation is used to validate the choice of variables. Figure 15 illustrate that the right variables are chosen. 58.32% of information is concentrated in both main component (F1 and F2).

Figure 15. Circle of correlation between variables and factors for chicken

From Figure 16 we observed that in day1 (Class1 chicken free), day3 (class2 chicken to become rotten) and day5, day7, day9 and day11 (class3 rotten chicken).

Figure 16. The result of PCA method after 11 days for rotten chicken

b. Identification by DFA method

From Figure 17 we observe that the three groups are well separated, and the observations within the same class are quite grouped together. Indeed, the grouping of classes is actually quite distinct around their centers of gravity with 82.29.5% success of classification.

Figure 17. The result of DFA method after 11 days for rotten chicken

In Figure 18 the degradation of chicken after defrosting are determined by comparing the thawed samples with our data base. The samples used in this experiment are frizzed during 10 days. According to the distance calculation with the DFA method we deduce the result exists in Table 2.

Figure 18. The result of DFA method for unknown samples

Table 2: The identification of unknown samples

Unknown Samples	Days	Result of identification
Test1	* After 1 hour of defrosting	* Class 1 “Fresh”
Test2	* After 6 hour of defrosting	* Class 3 “Rotten”
Test3	* After 4 hour of defrosting	* Class 3 “Rotten”
Test4	* After 2 hour of defrosting	* Class 2 “Begins to rot”

VI. IDENTIFICATION BETWEEN BEEF AND CHICKEN

We deduce from Figure 19 that we can identify between two types of meat are almost the same odor at rottenness by DFA method with a percentage of 78.88%.

Figure 19. Identification between chicken and beef using DFA method

Figure 20 used to compare the samples unknown with the data base. Table 3 below shows the validation of our result and identification between two meats is determinate by distance between unknown samples and class of each meat when DFA method is used.

Figure 20. Validation of identification between chicken and beef using DFA method

Table 3: The identification between beef and chicken

Unknown Samples	Days of degradation and type of meat	Result of identification	Square of distance
Test1	* Day1 for chicken	* Class 1 of chicken “Fresh”	40,073
Test2	* Day9 for beef	* Class 3 of beef “Rotten”	8,787
Test3	* Day4 for beef	* Class 2 of chicken “Begins to rot”	496,779
Test4	* Day3 for chicken	* Class 2 of chicken “Begins to rot”	17,162

VII. CONCLUSION

In this project, our objective is to identify between two rotten meat are almost the same odor using an electronic nose. The proposed design of electronic nose is a simple system with gas sensor and a digital sensor used to control humidity and temperature. A thorough database is built for better results. Classification and identification of these odors are realized by PCA and DFA methods. PCA it used to obtain a sufficient summary of the information contained in the initial table (database) and also gives a graphical representation of the data in classes but doesn't give a decision rule allowing to identify unknown samples. DFA is used to identify odor by calculating the distance between the unknown samples and class. This method also performs a good separation between classes. In this paper the survey of the degradation of each meat is done separately. Degradation after thawing is also studied. In future we wish to identify between other foods that have similar odor at rot. The final purpose of this work is to provide a device capable of detecting and identifying rotten foods, which can be very helpful in food quality control and very valuable for the consumer's health.

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